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Using magnetic nanoparticles Fe₃O₄ as a reusable catalyst for the synthesis of pyran and pyridine derivatives via one-pot multicomponent reaction

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Abstract

An atom-economical, efficient and mild protocol is described for the synthesis of 2-amino-3-cyanopyridine and 2-amino-3-cyano-4H-pyran derivatives in the presence of high surface area Fe₃O₄ as a highly effective heterogeneous catalyst via one-pot multicomponent cyclo-condensation reaction.

Keyword

Green chemistry, Magnetic nanoparticles Fe₃O₄, Multicomponent reaction, Pyran, Pyridine, Recyclable catalyst.